

Preparedness of Nepalese Academia for Society 5.0: A Study on Human Resources and Technology Transformation

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Abstract

Employing a deductive constructivist research design, the study selected a purposive convenient sampling method, targeting a sample size of 433 participants that represented a diverse spectrum of Nepalese academic sectors. Utilizing an online platform, a meticulously structured data collection instrument was administered. The deductive approach deliberately harmonized with the theoretical underpinnings of Society 5.0, thereby facilitating the systematic exploration of hypothesized relationships and constructs. Employing inferential statistical analyses through the use of SPSS software 24, and Amos 22, the collected data provided empirical insights into the prevailing state of preparedness within the realm of Nepalese academia. Consequently, the research design facilitated a thorough and in-depth examination of the readiness of the academic landscape in anticipation of the Society 5.0 paradigm shift within Nepalese educational institutions. In doing so, it made a substantial contribution by enriching both theoretical insights and practical comprehension of the intricate interplay between human resources and technological evolution. The present study demonstrates that academic institution readiness for Society 5.0 is a complex interplay of technological integration, innovative teaching methods, and potentially other unexplored factors. While technology integration in HR practices and innovative teaching methods exhibit significant impacts, the role of digital skills development appears nuanced, potentially requiring further investigation. This study provides valuable insights for educational leaders and policymakers aiming to enhance institutional readiness for the transformative era of Society 5.0.

Keywords: *HR, technology, Nepal, academia, digital, society 5.0*